

MSME Performance Integrative Model: The Influence of Human Resources Competence, Digital Marketing Strategy, and Financial Literacy on Business Sustainability with Entrepreneurial Orientation as a Mediation Variable

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to develop and test an integrative model of sustainability of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) by analyzing the influence of Human Resource Competence, Digital Marketing Strategy, and Financial Literacy on Business Sustainability through the mediation of Entrepreneurship Orientation. The study used a quantitative approach with the Structural Equation Modeling method based on Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM) on 400 MSME actors. The results of the analysis show that all constructs meet the criteria of validity and reliability. Structurally, HR Competencies, Digital Marketing Strategies, and Financial Literacy have a positive and significant effect on Business Sustainability. In addition, Entrepreneurial Orientation has been proven to play a role as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between internal capabilities and business sustainability. The value of the determination coefficient indicates that the model has a high explanatory power. These findings affirm the importance of integrating human resource capabilities, digital transformation, and financial literacy in creating competitive and sustainable MSMEs. This research contributes to the development of capability-based theories and provides practical implications for the formulation of integrative MSME empowerment policies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) occupy a strategic position in the global and national economic structure due to their significant contribution to job creation, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, and the reduction of regional economic inequality. Globally, MSMEs represent around 90% of business entities and absorb more than 50% of the world's workforce, and contribute significantly to the GDP of developing countries (Endris & Kassegn, 2022; Pardo Martínez & Cotte Poveda, 2022). In the Indonesian context, MSMEs are the backbone of the economy with a significant contribution to economic growth and labor absorption, as well as playing a role in poverty alleviation and strengthening the local economy (Hamdan, 2021; Mastintianto et al., 2025). However, this strategic role does not necessarily guarantee the sustainability of the business in the long term. MSMEs still face various structural obstacles such as limited access to financing, low quality of human resources (HR), weak financial literacy, and limitations in the adoption of

technology and digital marketing (Maheshkar & Soni, 2021; Budiman & Herkulana, 2021). The complexity of these challenges is increasing in the era of digitalization and global competition that demands integration between internal capabilities and entrepreneurial strategic orientation. Therefore, theoretical and empirical understanding of the integrative model of MSME performance and sustainability is an urgent research agenda to be developed more systematically.

Theoretically, the study of the performance and sustainability of MSMEs is largely rooted in the Resource-Based View (RBV) and its development, including the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV), which emphasizes the importance of valuable, rare, elusive, and irreplaceable resources as the basis for competitive advantage (Razzaque et al., 2023; Anaman et al., 2023). In the context of MSMEs, these resources are not only in the form of physical assets, but mainly in the form of human capital, managerial competence, and innovative capabilities that are internalized in the organization (Daat et

al., 2021; Rahman et al., 2024). On the other hand, the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) approach expands the understanding of performance by including social and environmental dimensions in addition to the economic dimension, so that business sustainability is not solely measured by profitability, but also by social contribution and environmental impact (M.P. et al., 2017). Empirical research shows that sustainable practices and green innovation can improve the competitiveness and long-term performance of MSMEs (Nirwal & Bhardwaj, 2025; Clemente - Almendros et al., 2025). Nevertheless, the relationship between sustainability practices and business performance is non-linear and contextual, even showing a U-shape pattern that demands long-term commitment before economic benefits can be felt (Clemente - Almendros et al., 2025). This fact indicates that the sustainability of MSME businesses cannot be separated from the integration of internal capabilities and the right strategic orientation.

One of the main determinants of MSME performance and sustainability is human resource competence based on Human Capital Theory. This theory asserts that individual knowledge, skills, experience, and abilities are forms of investment that increase organizational productivity and performance (Talip & Wasiuzzaman, 2023). In the context of MSMEs that tend to have a simple organizational structure and limited resources, the quality of human resources is a key factor that determines business competitiveness and resilience (Daat et al., 2021; Hamdan, 2021). Research shows that human resource competence has a significant effect on the performance of MSMEs both directly and through better financial management practices (Herawaty, 2023). In addition, entrepreneurial competence and managerial ability have been proven to mediate the influence of social capital on business performance Sutikno et al., (2022) and increase entrepreneurial orientation which ultimately strengthens competitiveness (Rahman et al., 2024a). Despite this, many MSMEs still face skills gaps, low levels of formal training, and weak managerial capacity, especially in micro enterprises (Kyal et al., 2021; Maheshkar & Soni, 2021). These limitations hinder the transformation of internal capabilities into optimal performance and sustainability.

In addition to human resource competence, digital marketing strategies and digital marketing capabilities are crucial factors in improving the performance of MSMEs in the era of technology-based economy. Business digitalization has been proven to contribute to environmental and economic sustainability through the mediation of sustainable practices (Miranda et al., 2024). The adoption of data-driven digital technologies and analytics is also positively correlated with sustainability-oriented actions, although the effects vary by size of the business (Hernández et al., 2024). In the Indonesian context, the adoption of social media and e-commerce has a positive effect on the performance of MSMEs and increases

entrepreneurial orientation (Yacob et al., 2023; Mastintianto et al., 2025). Digital marketing capabilities that include social media marketing, data analytics capability, and digital channel integration are part of the dynamic capabilities that enable MSMEs to adapt to market changes (Apasrawirote et al., 2022). However, measuring digital marketing ROI is still a challenge and often not integrated with the business strategy as a whole (Silva et al., 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2021). This shows that the effectiveness of a digital marketing strategy is not only determined by the adoption of technology, but also by the organization's capacity to manage and integrate it strategically.

On the other hand, financial literacy and financial capability are important determinants in business sustainability and entrepreneurial performance. Financial literacy which includes financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors allows business actors to make rational and strategic financial decisions (Eniola & Entebang, 2017; Goyal, 2024). Empirical research shows that financial literacy has a positive effect on entrepreneurial participation and business performance (Li & Qian, 2019; Munyuki & Jonah, 2021). In addition, financial literacy facilitates access to financing, reduces information asymmetry with financial institutions, and helps optimize capital structures (Hussain, 2018; Rijssen, 2023). In the context of Indonesian MSMEs, Islamic financial literacy and financial inclusion have been proven to improve business performance (Masrizal et al., 2024). However, the low level of financial literacy, especially among women entrepreneurs and remote areas, is still a significant obstacle (Christodoulou, 2024; Brimble, 2024). Therefore, financial literacy cannot be seen as a complementary variable, but as a foundation of financial capabilities that support business sustainability.

Although the literature has extensively discussed the influence of HR competencies, digital marketing strategies, and financial literacy on the performance of MSMEs partially there is still a research gap in integrating these three determinants in one comprehensive structural model. Most studies have examined the direct relationship between variables without considering mediation mechanisms that explain how internal capabilities translate into business performance and sustainability (Das et al., 2019; Rahman et al., 2024b). In fact, the Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) literature shows that entrepreneurial orientation acts as a resource mobilization mechanism that bridges internal capabilities and performance (Wolff et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2019). EO, which includes innovation, proactivity, and risk-taking, has been shown to mediate the influence of intellectual capital on competitiveness (Rahman et al., 2024), as well as mediate the relationship between e-commerce adoption and MSME performance (Yacob et al., 2023). However, there have not been many studies that have tested EO as a mediating variable in an integrative model that combines HR competencies, digital marketing strategies, and financial literacy to business sustainability.

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The main research gap in this study lies in the limitations of an empirical model that simultaneously examines the interaction between human resource competencies, digital marketing strategies, financial literacy, and entrepreneurial orientation in explaining the sustainability of MSME businesses. In addition, most previous research was conducted in the context of a specific country or sector without taking into account the characteristics of developing regions and islands that have limited infrastructure and market access. Previous studies have also shown that the relationship between sustainability practices and performance is influenced by the size of efforts and the intensity of innovation (Hernández et al., 2024; Clemente - Almendros et al., 2025), but have not explicitly integrated internal capability variables in a single conceptual framework based on SEM-PLS. Thus, there is a need to develop an integrative model based on a quantitative approach that is able to explain causal relationships simultaneously and test the role of entrepreneurial orientation mediation more comprehensively.

Based on this description, this study aims to develop and test an integrative model of MSME performance that analyzes the influence of human resource competencies, digital marketing strategies, and financial literacy on business sustainability with entrepreneurship orientation as a mediation variable. The theoretical contribution of this research lies in the integration of Human Capital Theory, Resource-Based View, and Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory in one comprehensive structural framework. Practically, this research is expected to provide policy implications for the development of MSMEs through strengthening human resource capacity, digital transformation, and improving financial literacy in an integrated manner. The formulation of the problem in this study is: How do HR competencies, digital marketing strategies, and financial literacy affect the sustainability of MSME businesses, and to what extent does entrepreneurial orientation mediate these relationships?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study uses a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design, which aims to test the causal relationship between variables in the integrative model of MSME performance. The quantitative approach was chosen because this research focuses on testing theory and developing structural models that integrate human resource (HR) competencies, digital marketing strategies, financial literacy, entrepreneurial orientation, and business sustainability. The analysis was carried out using Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) through the latest version of SmartPLS software. The PLS-SEM method was chosen because it is suitable for predictive model development research, is able to accommodate complex models with mediating variables, and does not require strict

data normality assumptions. In addition, PLS-SEM is effectively used in studies with medium sample sizes as well as models with reflective latent constructs.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study is all MSME actors registered with the Cooperatives and MSMEs Office in West Nusa Tenggara Province. The selection of this region is based on its characteristics as a developing region with an economic structure dominated by the MSME sector and facing the challenges of digital transformation and financial literacy. The sampling technique uses purposive sampling with the following criteria: (1) MSMEs have been operating for at least three years, (2) have at least two employees, (3) have used digital media in marketing activities, and (4) owners or managers are willing to be research respondents. Sample size determination refers to the PLS-SEM minimum rule, which is ten times the number of largest structural paths leading to a construct in the model. Taking into account the complexity of the model and the number of indicators, the targeted sample count is a minimum of 200 respondents to improve the stability of parameter estimation.

Data Collection Technique

The research data consists of primary data and secondary data. Primary data was collected through surveys using structured questionnaires that were disseminated in person or online. The questionnaire was designed using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The research instrument was developed based on indicators that have been validated in the previous literature. Human resource competence is measured through the dimensions of knowledge, skills, and managerial abilities. Digital marketing strategy is measured through the intensity of social media use, e-commerce utilization, digital analytics capabilities, and the integration of digital strategies in business. Financial literacy is measured through understanding financial management, budget planning, investment decision-making, and access to financing. Entrepreneurial orientation is measured by the dimensions of innovation, proactivity, and the courage to take risks. Business sustainability is measured through the dimensions of economic performance, growth stability, and long-term operational sustainability.

Data Analysis Techniques

Before the full-scale deployment, a pilot test was carried out on 30 MSME actors to ensure clarity of questions and test the initial validity. The validity and reliability test of the construct was carried out through the analysis of the outer model in PLS-SEM. Convergent validity was evaluated through outer loading values (>0.70) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE >0.50). The validity of the discriminant was tested using the Fornell-Larcker and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) criteria. The reliability of the construct was

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evaluated through the values of Composite Reliability (>0.70) and Cronbach's Alpha (>0.70). Indicators that do not meet the criteria will be phased out to obtain a valid and reliable measurement model.

Data analysis is carried out in two main stages, namely the evaluation of the measurement model and the evaluation of the structural model. In the structural model stage, tests were carried out on path coefficients, t-statistical values, and p-values using a bootstrapping procedure with 5,000 resamples. The R-squared value is used to measure the predictive ability of the model against endogenous variables. In addition, effect size (f-square) and predictive relevance (Q-square) were analyzed to assess the contribution strength of each construct. The entrepreneurial orientation mediation test was carried out by analyzing indirect effects and identifying the type of mediation (partial or full mediation) based on the significance of direct and indirect channels.

To ensure that there is no common method bias, testing is carried out through a full collinearity test with a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value <3.3 as a bias-free indicator. In addition, multicollinearity analysis between variables was also carried out to ensure the stability of the model. All analysis procedures follow SEM-PLS-based quantitative research reporting standards that are transparent and replicable.

Overall, the methodology of this research is designed to produce a robust integrative model in explaining the influence of human resource competencies, digital marketing strategies, and financial literacy on business sustainability through entrepreneurship-oriented mediation. The SmartPLS-based quantitative approach allows simultaneous testing of complex relationships and provides accurate parameter estimation in the context of MSMEs in developing regions. With this systematic and replicative methodological design, the research is expected to produce valid empirical findings and make theoretical and practical contributions in the development of MSME performance models based on internal capabilities.

Research Hypothesis

Based on the conceptual model developed, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: Human Resource Competence has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of MSME Businesses.

H2: Digital Marketing Strategy has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of MSME Businesses.

H3: Financial Literacy has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of MSME Businesses.

H4: Human Resource Competence has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation.

H5: Digital Marketing Strategy has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation.

H6: Financial Literacy has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation.

H7: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of MSME Businesses.

H8: Human Resource Competence Affects Business Sustainability through Entrepreneurship Orientation mediation.

H9: Digital Marketing Strategy affects Business Sustainability through the mediation of Entrepreneurial Orientation.

H10: Financial Literacy affects Business Sustainability through the mediation of Entrepreneurship Orientation.

Empirical Finding and Discussion

Description of Respondent Characteristics

This study involved 400 respondents who were MSME actors from various business sectors. The distribution of respondents by type of business is presented in Table 1. The table shows that the trade sector is the largest category with 126 respondents or around 31.5% of the total sample. The culinary sector occupies the second position with 96 respondents or 24%, followed by the service sector with 77 respondents or 19.25%. The production/manufacturing sector amounted to 58 respondents or 14.5%, while the other category amounted to 43 respondents or 10.75%. This composition shows that most of the respondents come from sectors that have a high level of market interaction. The dominance of the trade and culinary sectors indicates that marketing activities and consumer transactions are an important part of the characteristics of the study sample. With a relatively even distribution between sectors, the sample of this study reflects the diversity of representative MSME structures to be further analyzed in the structural model.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents by Type of Business

No	Type of Business	Quantity	Percentage
1	Services	77	19,25%
2	Culinary	96	24,00%
3	Trade	126	31,50%
4	Production / Manufacturing	58	14,50%
5	Others	43	10,75%
	Total	400	100%

Source: Processed data

The distribution of respondents based on the length of business is presented in Table 2. The table shows that the majority of businesses are in the age range of 1-6 years in almost all business sectors. In the trade sector, the highest number was found in the 4 - 6 year category, namely 40 respondents, followed by 35 respondents in 1 - 3 years. In the culinary sector, the 4 - 6 year old category also dominated with 30 respondents. The service sector shows a relatively balanced distribution between 1 - 3 years and 4 - 6 years. In

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the production/manufacturing sector, the majority are in the 4 - 6 year category, with 21 respondents. In general, this distribution shows that most MSMEs are in the early to medium growth phase. The existence of respondents with a business period of more than 10 years in each sector shows that there is a variation in the level of business maturity in the research sample.

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Length of Business

Type of Business	1-3 yrs	4-6 yrs	7-10 yrs	>10 Yrs	Total
Services	28	26	11	12	77
Culinary	26	30	10	18	96
Trade	35	40	32	19	126
Production	14	21	15	8	58
Others	6	15	9	13	43
Total					400

Source: Processed data

Evaluation of Measurement Models (Outer Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model was carried out to assess the validity and reliability of the indicators in each construct. The results of outer loading show that all indicators have values above 0.70. In the Business Sustainability (BS) construct, the loading value ranges from 0.922 to 0.945, which shows a very strong correlation between the indicator and the construct. The Digital Marketing Strategy Construct (DMS) has a loading range between 0.893 and 0.917. The Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) construct shows a loading value between 0.900 and 0.925. The Financial Literacy (FL) construct has a loading value between 0.875 and 0.909. The HR Competency Construct (HRC) has a loading value between 0.893 and 0.910. All of these values meet the criteria for convergent validity because they are above the threshold of 0.70. Thus, no indicators were eliminated in this evaluation stage.

The results of the convergent reliability and validity tests are presented in Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha value of the entire construct is above 0.96, which indicates a very high internal consistency. The composite reliability of the entire construct is also above 0.97, which signifies an excellent level of construct reliability. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of the entire variable was above 0.80, which is well above the minimum limit of 0.50. This shows that more than 80% of the variance of the indicators is explained by the latent constructs of each. These values indicate that the research instrument has a very strong measurement quality. Thus, the measurement model is eligible to proceed to the structural model evaluation stage.

Table 3. Convergent Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
BS	0.981	0.981	0.983	0.881
DMS	0.968	0.968	0.973	0.816
EO	0.972	0.972	0.976	0.836
FL	0.965	0.966	0.970	0.804
HRC	0.968	0.969	0.973	0.816

Source: SmartPLS4 processed data

Discriminatory validity testing was carried out using the HTMT criteria. The value of the HTMT between the constructs is entirely below the limit of 0.90, although the value between BS (Business Sustainability) and EO (Entrepreneurial Orientation) is close to the limit, which is 0.905. Other values range from 0.027 to 0.594. This shows that each construct has a fairly obvious difference from the other. Thus, the validity of the discriminator is acceptable. The evaluation of the outer model as a whole shows that the entire construct is valid and reliable. The measurement model was declared feasible for further structural analysis.

Evaluation of Structural Models (Inner Model)

The evaluation of structural models aims to test the relationships between latent variables in the research model. The results of the path coefficient are presented in Table 4. The relationship between DMS and BS has a coefficient of 0.294 with a t-statistic of 9.304 and a p-value of 0.000. The relationship between DMS and EO has a coefficient of 0.536 with a t-statistic of 20.024. The relationship between EO and BS has a coefficient of 0.478 with a t-statistic of 10.623. The relationship of FL to BS has a coefficient of 0.255 with a t-statistic of 7.796. The relationship between HRC and BS has a coefficient of 0.252 with a t-statistic of 8.379. The entire relationship showed a p-value of less than 0.05, which is statistically significant.

Table 4. Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O / STDEV)	P values
DMS -> BS	0.294	0.295	0.032	9.304	0.000
DMS -> EO	0.536	0.535	0.027	20.024	0.000
EO -> BS	0.478	0.477	0.045	10.623	0.000

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FL					
->	0.255	0.256	0.033	7.796	0.000
BS					
FL					
->	0.514	0.514	0.028	18.665	0.000
EO					
HRC					
->	0.252	0.253	0.030	8.379	0.000
BS					
HRC					
->	0.468	0.468	0.026	17.720	0.000
EO					

Source: SmartPLS4 processed data

The R-square value for the Business Sustainability construct is 0.831, which means that 83.1% of the variation in the construct can be explained by the variables in the model. The R-square value for Entrepreneurship Orientation is 0.767, indicating that the model explains 76.7% of the variance. The value of f-square indicates that EO has the largest contribution to BS of 0.316. The Q-square value for BS of 0.775 and for EO of 0.764 indicates the model's high predictive ability. An SRMR value of 0.025 indicates an excellent level of model suitability. An NFI value of 0.952 indicates that the model has a strong match with empirical data. Overall, the structural model shows excellent estimation quality. To provide a comprehensive overview of the results of the analysis, the following presents a model of PLS-SEM estimation results consisting of an outer model and an inner model.

Figure 1. Outer Model

Figure 1 shows the results of the estimation of the outer model which contains the outer loading value of each indicator against the latent construct. All indicators in the construct of Human Resources Competency (HRC), Digital Marketing Strategy (DMS), Financial Literacy (FL), Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), and Business Sustainability (BS) have a loading value above 0.70. The loading value in the HRC construct is in the range of 0.893–0.910. DMS constructs

have a range of 0.893–0.917. The FL construct has a range of 0.875–0.909. EO constructs have a range of 0.900–0.925. The BS construct has a range of 0.922–0.945. These values show a very strong correlation between the indicator and its construct. No indicators were eliminated because they all met the criteria for convergent validity.

Figure 2. Inner Model (Structural Model)

Figure 2 shows a structural model with the value of the path coefficient and the value of R-square in the endogenous construct. The R-square value in the Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) construct is 0.767. This value shows that 76.7% of EO variations are explained by HRC, DMS, and FL. The R-square value in the Business Sustainability (BS) construct is 0.831. This value shows that 83.1% of BS variations are explained by HRC, DMS, FL, and EO. The entire structural path shows a positive coefficient value. The p-value of the entire path is 0.000 which indicates statistical significance at the level of 5%. The structural model shows a strong causal relationship between constructs.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study show that an integrative model that examines the influence of Human Resource Competency (HRC), Digital Marketing Strategy (DMS), and Financial Literacy (FL) on Business Sustainability (BS) with Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) as a mediating variable has a very good level of model compatibility. The R-square value of 0.831 in the business sustainability construct shows that 83.1% of the variability of business sustainability can be explained by the variables in the model. This figure reflects the high power of the model in explaining the determinants of MSME sustainability. These findings strengthen the Resource-Based View (RBV) argument that the combination of valuable and hard-to-replicate internal resources is a major factor in the creation of competitive advantage and long-term performance (Razzaque et al., 2023; Anaman et al., 2023). In this context, human resource competencies, digital capabilities, and financial literacy are strategic resources that form the foundation of business sustainability. In addition, the high Q-square value indicates the model's strong

predictive ability, so that the model not only explains causal relationships but also has predictive power over future performance. Thus, the results of this study support a capability-based approach as a relevant theoretical framework in understanding the dynamics of MSMEs in developing regions.

The significant and positive influence of Digital Marketing Strategy on Business Sustainability shows that digital transformation plays an important role in strengthening the competitiveness of MSMEs. The path coefficient of 0.294 indicates that increasing the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies contributes directly to business sustainability. These findings are in line with research by Miranda et al. (2024) which shows that business digitalization contributes to economic and environmental sustainability through the integration of digital practices. In addition, Hernández et al. (2024) emphasized that the adoption of data-based technology improves the ability of MSMEs to respond to market changes. In this study, the power of DMS's influence on EO (0.536) was even greater than the direct influence on BS, which shows that digital strategies not only have a direct impact on performance, but also form entrepreneurial orientation as a mechanism for internalizing digital capabilities. This indicates that digital marketing is not just a promotional tool, but a strategic instrument that forms the innovative and proactive attitude of business actors. Thus, these findings reinforce the view that digital capability is part of dynamic capabilities that allow organizations to adapt to a competitive environment (Apasrawirote et al., 2022).

The effect of financial literacy on business sustainability also showed significant results with a coefficient of 0.255. These findings support the research of Eniola and Entebang (2017), which emphasizes that financial literacy improves the ability to make rational financial decisions. Financial literacy allows businesses to manage cash flow, plan investments, and control business risks more systematically (Li & Qian, 2019; Munyuki & Jonah, 2021). In the context of this study, financial literacy also had a strong effect on entrepreneurial orientation (0.514), which shows that financial understanding not only has an impact on financial stability, but also encourages the courage to take risks and innovate. This indicates that financial literacy acts as a catalyst that strengthens entrepreneurial behavior. These findings are consistent with (Hussain (2018) who stated that financial literacy reduces information asymmetry and improves access to financing. In addition, these results are consistent with those of Masrizal et al. (2024), who found that financial literacy improves the MSMEs' performance in Indonesia. Thus, financial literacy is a fundamental element in building resilient business sustainability.

Human resource competence shows a positive influence on business sustainability with a coefficient of 0.252. These results support Human Capital Theory, which emphasizes that the quality of human resources is the main determinant

of organizational productivity and performance (Talip & Wasiuzzaman, 2023). Managerial competence, technical skills, and decision-making skills enable business actors to manage resources effectively (Daat et al. (2021). In addition, the influence of HRC on EO of 0.468 shows that HR competencies contribute to forming an innovative and proactive entrepreneurial orientation. These findings are in line with Rahman et al., (2024) who show that intellectual capital mediates competitiveness through entrepreneurial orientation. Thus, HR competence is not only an operational factor, but also a strategic factor that shapes the entrepreneurial culture in the organization. In the context of MSMEs, improving the quality of human resources is a long-term investment that determines business sustainability. Therefore, strengthening human resource capacity is an important implication in the development of MSME policies. The role of Entrepreneurship Orientation mediation in this study is a central finding that strengthens the integration of the theory. The EO coefficient to BS of 0.478 shows that entrepreneurial orientation is a strong determinant of business sustainability. These results are consistent with Wolff et al. (2015) and Sun et al., (2019) who stated that EO contributes significantly to company performance. In this model, EO mediates the influence of DMS, FL, and HRC on business sustainability. This shows that internal capabilities do not automatically produce performance, but require an innovative, proactive, and risk-taking attitude to be actualized into performance. In other words, EO serves as a transformational mechanism that connects resources to business outcomes. These findings fill in the gaps of previous research that tested more direct relationships without mediation mechanisms ((Das et al., 2019b). Thus, the main contribution of this research is the development of an integrative model based on EO mediation.

The effect size value (f-square) shows that EO has the largest contribution to BS (0.316), compared to other variables. This confirms that entrepreneurial orientation is the dominant factor in the model. In addition, the R-square value of 0.767 on EO shows that DMS, FL, and HRC are able to explain 76.7% of the variation in entrepreneurial orientation. These findings show that entrepreneurial orientation is formed from a combination of digital, financial, and human resource capabilities. The integration of these three factors strengthens the capability-based view approach in explaining the performance of MSMEs. Thus, this study not only tests the theory but also develops a more comprehensive model than previous studies. This integrative model broadens the understanding of the interaction between capabilities in the context of MSMEs. Therefore, this research has a theoretical contribution in the development of a capability-based entrepreneurship model.

The practical implications of these findings show that the development of MSMEs cannot be done partially. Human resource competency improvement programs need to be

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synergized with digital marketing and financial literacy training. Local governments and MSME support institutions need to design integrated policies that strengthen these three aspects simultaneously. This approach will create a synergistic effect in improving entrepreneurial orientation and business sustainability. In addition, MSME actors need to realize that investment in human resources, digitalization, and financial literacy is a sustainable long-term strategy. Thus, the results of this study provide policy recommendations based on empirical evidence. The integration of capability-based policies will strengthen the competitiveness of MSMEs at the regional and national levels.

Although the model shows high strength, this study has limitations. First, the study uses a cross-sectional approach so that it cannot capture the dynamics of long-term change. Second, research is limited to one region so generalizations need to be done carefully. Third, external variables such as macroeconomic and regulatory factors are not included in the model. Fourth, the research uses a quantitative approach so that it does not explore qualitative aspects in depth. Therefore, further research can use longitudinal and mixed-method approaches to enrich the analysis. In addition, the expansion of variables such as green innovation and environmental sustainability can enrich the model. Thus, this research opens up space for further development in the study of entrepreneurship and MSMEs.

Overall, the results of this study show that the sustainability of MSME businesses is shaped by the integration of human resource competencies, digital marketing strategies, financial literacy, and entrepreneurial orientation. The developed model is able to explain most of the variations in business sustainability with an excellent level of validity and reliability. These findings strengthen the integration of Human Capital Theory, Resource-Based View, and Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory in one comprehensive framework. A major theoretical contribution lies in the mediation testing of entrepreneurial orientation in the relationship between internal capabilities and business sustainability. Practically, this research provides an empirical basis for the development of capability-based MSME policies. Thus, this research makes a significant contribution to the development of entrepreneurship literature in the context of developing regions. The resulting integrative model can be a reference for further research and MSME development practices.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This research proves that Human Resource Competence, Digital Marketing Strategy, and Financial Literacy have a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of MSME Businesses. Entrepreneurship Orientation plays a role as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between internal capabilities and business sustainability. The model

developed has high explainability, showing that the integration of HR, digital, and financial capabilities is the main determinant of the sustainability of MSMEs.

Theoretically, this study integrates Human Capital Theory, Resource-Based View, and Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory in one comprehensive, empirically validated model. Practically, the results of the study emphasized the importance of human resource capacity development, digital transformation, and increasing financial literacy simultaneously to create resilient and competitive MSMEs.

Further research is suggested to test this model in different regional contexts and use a longitudinal approach to strengthen generalizations and understanding of business sustainability dynamics.

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